

Characteristics of a Profession

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Forewords

In Québec, 54 professions are governed by the Professional Code and supervised by 46 professional orders. As stipulated in article 25 of the Professional Code, several aspects must be considered to determine whether a profession should be regulated and supervised by a professional order. The factors taken into account are mainly related to the nature of the professional activities in question and the characteristics of the individuals who practise them:

- The knowledge required in order to engage in the activities
- The degree of independence enjoyed by the persons practising the activities and the difficulty which persons not having the same training and qualifications would have in assessing those activities
- The personal nature of the relationships between such persons and those having recourse to their services, by reason of the special trust which the latter must place in them
- The gravity of the prejudice which might be sustained by those who have recourse to the services of such persons, because their competence was not supervised by an order
- The confidential nature of the information to which such persons are made privy in the course of practising their profession - Québec Inter professional Council definition.

Characteristics of a Profession

In a profession, autonomy and self-regulation still hold true or are even desirable in the modern corporate and bureaucratic world.

A profession's right to exist, along with the power and privileges its members enjoy, rests upon the professions upholding of public values through the development, transmission and application of a body of knowledge.

The creation of this body of knowledge and its concentration in the hands of a few creates a knowledge gap between the professional and client. That gap gives the profession power. Such power is reinforced by differential access to other resources -technological, physical and organizational. For example, it is not just medical knowledge but access to medical technology that gives the medical profession its capacity to heal. It is the institutional links to courts that make barristers so effective.

The knowledge differential is deliberately created and increased to further the power of the profession. However, once power differentials are created for whatever reason, there is a reluctance to give them up and there remains a temptation to use them for personal gain, either at the expense of the client or in some cases to the mutual enrichment of professional and client at the expense of the wider public.

Controlling the use and abuse of that power is one of the principle concerns of the community and one of the principle purposes for professional ethics.

The fundamental question concerning any profession receiving public support and privileges is how can that support, and its continuation, be justified.

That justification cannot be in terms of the benefits the profession confers on its members but the benefits the profession confers on the general public. The argument is that an educated group of specialists developing, transmitting and applying a specialist body of knowledge will use that knowledge to benefit the broader community.

This argument builds upon the ideal that the establishment and sustenance of a profession involves a social compact with society, granting privileges such as autonomy, self-regulation, monopolistic rights and public funding of professional education in return for the provision of desirable social goods.

The provision is that the profession places 'the public interest foremost, even if serving the public interest may at times be at the professionals' own expense'. Crucially, different public values and interests will apply to different professions and should be seen as embodied in the very definition of these professions.

For example, the medical profession and its privileges are justified by the values of preserving life and health. The legal profession and its privileges are justified by the values of upholding justice, the rule of law and the rights of the individual. It is easy to be cynical about such claims but there is little doubt that most professionals believe them and, for the most part try to act upon them.

Professional Minimum Standards

At each stage of the behavioural continuum it is necessary to look at the means by which values are articulated, enforced and reinforced. It is emphasized the latter because praise and rewards are the most important means of promoting and realizing values.

It should also be necessary to identify temptations, conflicts and dilemmas specific to the type of profession, the type of practice and the individual standing within the behavioural continuum.

It is important to highlight the fact that different levels of the continuum require different levels of specificity, different sanctions (positive and/or negative) and different institutional interpretation and enforcement:

At the lowest levels of the behavioural continuum, the sanctions are greatest - including fines, imprisonment and public opprobrium. The criminal law is designed as a means for indicating the opprobrium of society for certain kinds of actions and the attachment of that opprobrium to those who are proven to have performed them.

To be effective and just, formal sanction and social opprobrium require clear and prior statements of the maximum possible precision, endorsed by the highest authority (which is, in a democracy, at the very least the representative parliament and sometimes an elected president as well).

The authoritative interpretation and enforcement of these rules must be by a justice system on which the highest standards of procedural fairness are imposed.

The profession will set minimum standards for membership of the profession and procedures for detecting breaches. These minimal values are those of the profession so that the profession is, in general, the appropriate body to define, interpret and enforce them.

These minimal professional standards will obviously be higher than those required to escape criminal sanction.

The requirements of precise (and prior) definition, social endorsement and procedural fairness do not apply so rigidly to the policing of minimal professional standards. However, in recognition of the costs both financial and to reputation of being expelled from a profession, there needs to be procedural fairness, independence and precision in the definition and application of those norms whose breach can lead to expulsion or suspension.

It is not necessary for the court to actually enforce these norms although it may act in its supervisory capacity to ensure that the profession procedures reach appropriate standards of fairness and legality.

Moving up the scale of professional behaviour to the 'standard aspiration' of good practice, the profession should retain an important role in setting such standards, particularly those that improve service to clients and realize the values that justify the profession existence.

Although it is not the role of the profession to punish an individual for failing to meet these higher standards, the profession should be involved in encouraging all its members to aspire to these ideals. Institutions that can play a vital role in this regard include all the places in which professional work, including the agency, firm, practice, company and hospital.

As institutions they will generally be concerned to ensure that 'best practice' is, as far as possible, promoted and achieved.

They have a clear financial and legal interest in monitoring both overall performance and the work of individual professionals as employees.

In pursuing these objectives, how much attention should the institution give to the goal of furthering values of the profession?

The answer is that if the profession is to move up the normative and behavioural continuum from 'just good enough to avoid prosecution or disbarment' towards the inspirational standards of good practice, the firm must pay much more attention to furthering the values of professions.

It is at this level that there is a great deal of criticism of professions. For example, the structure of legal institutions, especially law firms, is a major impediment to individual reflection and the realization in daily practice of the higher values of the profession.

The modern catch-cry that 'law is big business' encapsulates the potential for conflict between professional values and business interests/maximization of profits.

The rise of the American practice of monitoring and judging the performance of employee solicitors (and later partners) on the basis of the number of 'billable hours' rightly raises concerns about the temptation to overcharge or otherwise engage in sharp practice.

The problem is strikingly simple. Whatever the firm public position on professional values, if it judges and promotes its own employees on the basis of their money-raising ability, then it is very obviously pursuing profit maximization at the expense of professional values. We would argue that such a firm should forfeit the right to be seen as an organization of professionals and to enjoy the associated regulatory privileges.

Improving Professional or Institutional Behaviour

Improving professional or institutional behaviour (and avoiding misbehaviour) requires a coordinated approach based on a 'trinity' of ethical standard setting, legal regulation and institutional reform.

Such an approach recognizes that professional behaviour falls into a normative continuum from the highest professional standards, through good work, sub-par work, misconduct and criminality. It also recognizes that there is a professional practice range from solo to large group settings and that there are many distinctions among professionals important for ethical issues.

The goal of the 'trinity' is to raise individual professionals as far up the normative continuum as possible, using means appropriate to the particular profession and work setting.

A individual self-assessment as the basis for determining continuing competence is a good example of a focus on continually lifting standards within a profession. Such a strategy is far more likely to be successful than a policy of deterrence based on punitive sanctions.

Not only is it obviously better to avoid the opportunity for ethical failings than to deal with their consequences, there is some evidence that punishment can in fact be counterproductive. Imposing criminal sanctions, society should not primarily emphasize community disgust at the behaviour condemned.

Rather society should emphasize the positive values of the profession (and society) that have been betrayed. This is the reason why the individual has received a higher level of punishment than others who were not professionally committed to those values.

The majority of individuals (the 'virtuous actors'), an appeal to reason (persuasion) will be sufficient. The assumption is that the threat of deterrence in its various forms will be sufficient for the 'rational actor'.

What is vital is the co-ordination of the various approaches to improving behaviour to shift as much behaviour as high up the behavioural scale as possible. Ethical standards should set out the inspirational goals at the highest levels of the behavioural continuum; **disciplinary codes and criminal sanctions should be addressed to the lowest levels of the behavioural field.**

Even for those who do not reach the highest ideals of the profession, other means should underpin and reward higher standards at all levels. The more successful a co-ordinate approach based on ethical standard - setting, legal regulation and institutional reform, the higher the overall standards of the profession and the fewer professionals at the lower levels committing crimes and ethical breaches.

Thus, in a well-ordered profession, the aspirations of most practitioners will be to strive for the highest standards of the profession and this focus will keep individuals so far from the sanction minimum that there will be very few breaches, even by those who fall below the average.

Criminal behaviour will also be rarer if the occurrence of institutional temptations or dilemmas is reduced. The more effective is ethical standard setting and ethical education, the lesser the opportunity to resort to the excuse of ignorance.

And the more effective is institutional reform, the less likely the profession acceptance of the excuse that the individual faced an ethical dilemma, alone and unsupported.